

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FACTORS AFFECTING ACADEMIC READING COMPREHENSION OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article is aimed at revealing the factors that affect the academic reading comprehension of high school students. There are objective (e.g. the limited amount of knowledge of high school students) and subjective factors (e.g. students of their background knowledge). The level of formation of academic reading is evidenced by the possession of different reading strategies. Students need to acquire effective strategies for academic reading, the structure of an academic text, and how to recognize discourse markers for a faster initial acquaintance with the material.

Keywords: academic reading, academic literacy, reading comprehension, reading strategies, process of reading, academic reading skills, types of reading.

Modern requirements for teaching English in high school include the development of academic skills. Kazakhstan's participation in the Bologna process and the adaptation of the European education system contribute to the fact that a foreign language becomes not only an obligatory component of education, but also a tool for acquiring knowledge. Thus, the development of academic skills allows high school students to master the language of their future specialty, freely navigate in the academic environment and, as a result, successfully carry out professional communication in English in future.

Popular science texts are used quite early in the educational process at high school, which can be based on common vocabulary studied at academic reading classes and are typical for any style. The simplicity/complexity of the text for students is primarily due to the absence/presence of unknown language units in it. Unknown language material can be considered as an objective factor in mastering reading in a foreign language, since this or that text is intended for reading in a group of certain training, and those language units that are not familiar to students, as a rule, have not been studied by them. Comprehension of what is read is carried out easily and is effective when students either do not encounter unfamiliar units in the text, or their number is insignificant.

Thus, mastering the skill of academic reading seems to be one of the goals of teaching a foreign language to students from high school. Many authors agree on the significance of reading skill in developing many other skills. For example, Merga & Roni (2018) claim that reading skill can promote lifelong education and training.

Academic reading is a special kind of reading aimed at extracting information from texts of popular science and scientific speech styles, analyzing the structure of a scientific text. It is believed that the ability to read academic texts involves the mastery of the student not only in general reading skills and abilities. It is assumed that he has at least a basic knowledge of

the discipline he has chosen as his future specialty at high school. However, the main purpose of academic reading in a foreign language is to determine how well the student has learned to use the language to solve academic problems.

Academic reading is considered a more complex process than general reading, especially for schoolchildren, since texts are loaded with terminology and complex grammar. In order to solve an educational problem, high school students need not only to read a text and understand its content, but also comprehend involves an ability to interact with the text by predicting what happens next using clues in the text, identifying the main ideas of text, link them together and establishing logical connections between facts. Kim (2017) assumes reading as a complex process consisting of not only vocabulary and grammar knowledge, but also of cognitive skills and abilities, comprising working memory, inhibitory control, attentional control, inference, perspective taking, and comprehension monitoring.

There are objective and subjective factors affecting academic reading comprehension of high school students. The objective factors include the limited amount of knowledge of high school students that does not allow the use of texts in the educational process that are complex in terms of the information. As noted by many authors, it is easier to understand information that reflects activities close to students. The presence in the text of unfamiliar realities specific to a given country can cause difficulties in understanding if the student does not have sufficient awareness of what is being described. As in the native language, the closer the range of concepts used by the author to what is in the experience of the reader, the easier it is for him to understand the text in a foreign language.

The presence of new language material in the text has a significant impact on the processes of understanding an academic text. It is important not only the number of new lexical units, but also their qualitative characteristics in the transfer of the content of the text. The

presence of such units slows down understanding, since they draw the attention of students to the language material. Understanding an academic text in a foreign language also depends on the presence of unknown or complex grammar structures in the text. If in the native language grammatical forms rarely make it difficult to understand, then when mastering a foreign language, their ignorance or complexity often causes a misunderstanding of the semantic relationships between words and sentences. The well-known grammatical material and the simplicity of the constructions used in the text not only provide an opportunity to understand it accurately and quickly, but also allow students to correctly set the meaning of lexical units and use the dictionary rationally.

The subjective factors in the formation of academic reading skills in a foreign language involve the use by students of their background knowledge. If the student correlates the incoming information with the information he possesses, then he more easily can interpret and evaluate the facts. There are also certain psychological factors associated with reading and understanding academic texts that affect the adequate understanding of foreign scientific texts. This problem is also the object of study by foreign researchers.

Today, the problem of understanding is one of the main problems that students encounter when they encounter various texts during their studies. One of the most important tasks of the teacher is precisely the choice of such a text, which, in terms of its complexity, would be adequate to the level of preparedness of students. Kendeou et al. (2016) emphasize the role of the word processing in the reading comprehension as readers identify its phonological, orthographical, and semantic representations.

According to N.V. Smirnova (2015), academic literacy is not limited to a set of reading and writing skills, but is a way of thinking suitable for a particular cultural environment, it is a kind of complex structural formation that integrates both traditional knowledge and intellectual, communicative, worldview skills [p. 59]. At the same time, special attention is focused on the methods of comprehending information, its cognitive analysis and text processing.

Reading a scientific text is interpreted by the readers based on their own experience of perception of the information received. The problem also lies in the insufficient formation of high school students' skills, first of all, analytical reading. Analytical reading is an educational type of reading focused on the formation of analytical and interpretive abilities of students. At the first stage, various types of information are extracted, at the second, it is comprehended and evaluated based on the background knowledge of students, which presents certain difficulties for high school students, since they do not yet have scientific experience in the relevant field of knowledge. Such experience is acquired both in the process of working with texts of various scientific genres.

The next important factor is developing by students the effective strategies for academic reading. The level of formation of academic reading is evidenced by the possession of different reading strategies. The

teacher, therefore, faces the need to teach students effective strategies for academic reading. Reading is a specific form of linguistic communication of people through printed or handwritten texts, one of the main forms of mediated communication. Skimming is understanding of the main content of an academic text; recognition of the structure of the text, highlighting its semantic parts (beginning, main part, conclusion); establishing semantic links within a paragraph and between paragraphs. Scanning involves search and identification of the necessary information: digital data, formulas, terms and concepts, definitions. approaches to the designated problem, etc.

Modern theory of foreign language education considers that for a deep and complete understanding of the text, high school students need to learn how to work with it at three stages: before, during reading and after it. The student looks through keywords, titles of sections, tables, diagrams and illustrations. Each of the types of reading is appropriate to use at its stage: pre-text, text and post-text. The primary reading of the text is introductory in nature, the first task before reading is given to understand the general content of the text or its key points, while setting a strict time frame for reading the text. At the pre-text stage, first of all, prognostic skills are formed: work with the title and keywords is organized. Students make assumptions about the theme of the text and offer a kind of logical framework for the text, based on keywords.

At the text stage, during the first reading, attention is directed to understanding the main content/main idea of the text and dividing it into semantic parts. In the process of reading, students can write down the main thoughts or write out key words/phrases, and then make a plan (in the form of sentences/phrases). Text work defines settings that contain indications of the technology used, the speed and the need to solve certain cognitive and communicative tasks in the process of reading. The semantic side of reading implies understanding by the reader:

- the main meaning of the entire content of the text;
- meanings of words used in the text, both literally and figuratively;
- the content of each of the sentences included in the text, clarification of the semantic connection between the sentences.

At the post-text stage of working with an academic text, productive skills are formed to use the extracted content for subsequent scientific communication, that is, to create a secondary text (abstract, report, annotation, etc.). In other words, the material of the primary academic text becomes a linguistic (speech) content support for the development of skills in oral and written speech process.

Post-text work is focused on checking reading comprehension, monitoring the degree of formation of reading skills and the possible use of the information received in future professional activities.

Summing up, it should be emphasized that academic reading brings reading as a complex type of speech activity to a qualitatively new level of understanding of an academic text, not only the extraction of

factual information (general understanding of the content), but, above all, the ability to compose and subject-logical analysis of texts. Thus, the factors that affect the academic reading comprehension of high school students are developing effective strategies for academic reading, helping students understand the structure of an academic text, and recognize discourse markers for a faster work with the material.

When mastering academic reading in a foreign language, an additional factor appears that negatively affects understanding, the focus of the reader's attention on the linguistic material of the text. The influence of a number of psychological factors that contribute to the flow of understanding processes is absent during the development of reading in a foreign language. The task of the teacher is to teach students to identify and combine previous knowledge, to study new vocabulary before reading the text, to explain key concepts, to highlight the main ideas, to give tasks for reading comprehension.

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